

ISic3362

Inscribed stele in the Sikel language

Language

Sikel

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

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Autopsy

2013.09.30

Last Change

2017-10-07 - Jonathan Prag removed seg elements introduced for bilingual edition

Place of origin (ancient)

near Euboia (?)

Place of origin (modern)

near Licodia Eubea

Provenance

Found in 1929 in the area of an

ancient necropolis in contrada Sciri
Sottano , 10km
south-west of Licodia Eubea

Coordinates

37.11507, 14.60573

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 47071

Physical Description

A slab of limestone, narrower at the base, and rounded at the top; the bottom edge is roughly straight. The surface is roughly smoothed. There is minor damage to the face in the upper left quarter.

Dimensions

Height 76 cm

Width 46 cm

Depth 7 cm

Layout

The text is arranged in a clockwise spiral, beginning at the lower left corner, and running right around the outer margin of the face, before proceeding up the left side for a second time.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Greek letters, including 'alpha siculum' □

Letter heights:

Not measured: mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. ΝΕΝΔΑΣ Π,Υ []ΣΤΕΒΕΓΠΡΑΑΡΕΙΕΝΒΟ[]ΡΕΝΑΙΦΙΔΕΠΑΓΟΣΤΙΚΕΑΙΤΕ[]ΛΥΒΕ
1. nendas p,υ []stebegpraareienbo[]renaividepagostikeaite[]lube

Apparatus

Text after Agostiniani 1992

Translation (en)

Translation (it)

Commentary

The text is probably a funerary inscription. The letters do not run left-to-right, but in a spiral, beginning at the bottom left (a feature also found in some early Greek inscriptions). The initial word Nendas is found in other Sikel inscriptions and usually thought to be a personal name. According to ancient authors such as Thucydides, the Sikels were one of three ethnic groups present on the island before the arrival of the Phoenicians and Greeks. A small number of inscriptions from the sixth and fifth centuries BC have been found in the south-east of the island, including this one. These use the Greek alphabet (with the distinctive form of alpha α visible here) but appear to be in the Sikel language – in other words, the practice of writing appears to have been adopted from the Greek settlers. The Sikel language is considered to be similar to the Sabellic languages of central Italy.

Digital identifiers:

TM 644867

Bibliography

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Photo J. Prag